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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Presentación de un modelo práctico para la prevención de la victimización sexual de niños y adolescentes en Irán: síntesis de investigación **DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7114623**

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Resumen

Las tasas de abuso infantil suelen ser más bajas que en el mundo. Los estudios en Irán muestran que el 10% ha sido violado al menos una vez en su vida. La mayoría de las violaciones no se denuncian por varias razones, y solo 344 de cada 1000 violaciones se denuncian a la policía. En otras palabras, de tres casos, dos permanecen ocultos. En 2013, 561 personas fueron encarceladas en Irán por delitos relacionados con la violencia sexual infantil, situación que aumentó a 2683 en 2021. Las sobrevivientes de violación, tienen menos probabilidades de buscar tratamiento postraumático, solo el 26% busca atención médica, por lo que el aumento de delitos sexuales en Irán muestra la necesidad de mayores esfuerzos para estudiar estrategias de prevención. Se trata de una investigación cuyo propósito fue presentar un modelo práctico para la prevención del abuso sexual en niños y adolescentes en Irán. Los datos fueron recolectados a través de un cuestionario elaborado por el investigador en secciones cuantitativas y cualitativas. Las pruebas de chi-cuadrado y la de Fisher permitieron analizar los datos del cuestionario utilizando el software estadístico SPSS (versión 18). Los resultados mostraron que ocho factores sociales, económicos, de género, familiares, demográficos, mediáticos, psicológicos y biológicos pueden jugar un papel en la victimización sexual de niños y adolescentes.

Palabras clave: modelo de prevención, victimización sexual, síntesis de investigación, niñez, adolescencia.

Abstract

Presenting a Practical Model for the Prevention of Sexual Victimization of Children and Adolescents in Iran: Research Synthesis

Child abuse rates are often lower than in the real world while social problems are hidden. Studies in Iran show that 10% of children have been raped at least once in their life. Most rapes are not reported to the police for various reasons, with only 344 out of 1,000 rapes being reported to the police. In other words, out of three cases, two remain hidden. In 2013, 561 people were imprisoned in Iran for crimes related to child sexual violence, which will increase to 2683 in 2021. Rape survivors, on the other hand, are less likely to seek post-traumatic treatment, with only 26% of victims. Seek medical attention, for which the increase in sexual crimes in Iran shows the need for greater efforts to study prevention strategies and postpone and reduce these crimes. This research is applied in terms of purpose and descriptive survey in terms of execution method. The purpose of

this study is to present a practical model for the prevention of sexual abuse of children and adolescents in Iran. For this, the data was collected through a combination of research and a questionnaire prepared by the researcher in quantitative and qualitative sections, respectively. The chi-square test and Fisher's exact test were used to analyze the questionnaire data using the statistical software SPSS (version 18). The results of a combination of investigations showed that eight factors like social, economic, gender, family, demographic, media, psychological and biological can play a role in the sexual victimization of children and adolescents.

Keywords: prevention model, sexual victimization, research synthesis, children, adolescents.

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1.- Introduction

The rising trend in sexual offences in Iran calls for much more efforts to reflect on prevention strategies, and consequently moderate such crimes because of their undesirable consequences, such as loss of a sense of security, weak family structure, widespread lawlessness in the society, and thus hurting the feelings in the public (Towhidi & Fazli, 2014: 72). The starting point of criminology is to identify the effective factors in crime incidence in order for providing prevention strategies, and then developing correctional treatment, accordingly (Mirkhalili, 2009: 35).

Therefore, it is of utmost importance to find the factors affecting the occurrence of such crimes and take action to eradicate them. The increasing prevalence rate of sexual deviations in recent years also indicates the uselessness of the legislative response to sexual offenses and misconduct. In spite of the uncontrollable growth of sexual crimes in the society, they have not still received much attention from experts in various fields for unknown reasons (Towhidi & Fazli, 2014: 72). The strategies that have been adopted so far to deal with sexual victimization have been merely subjective, cross-sectional, superficial, short-term, and without any real and comprehensive pathology (Paknahad, 2013: 30).

As children and adolescents are psychologically and socially more sensitive, and are even much more vulnerable than other age groups, and considering that the progress and development in any society largely depends on public health, the research on the phenomenon of sexual victimization to detect the causes of crimes and offences is very important because it contributes to detecting the shortcomings and taking action to solve these problems. In this way, the challenges facing the society, particularly the future generations as the most sensitive but flexible groups can be resolved, and some strategies can be implemented to advance the scientific and cultural goals in the society

(Torabi & Rezazadeh Moghaddam, 2017). Accordingly, the present study was to fulfill Paragraph 5 of Article 156 of the Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Iran, i.e., "Appropriate action needs to be taken to prevent crime and reform criminals", and use a method applicable to these individuals. In this regard, the practical model for the prevention of sexual victimization of children and adolescents in Iran was presented.

2. Theoretical Foundation

Prevention: Definition and Concept

The term prevention literally means "a preventive action, repulsion, obstruction, and forbidding maintenance and wanting" (Dekhoda, 1998: 5991). In English, it refers to the action of stopping something from happening or arising (Rajabipour, 2008: 70). With reference to the concept of prevention, there are two general orientations: broad and narrow or limited. According to the broad concept, "any action taken against a crime to reduce is considered prevention". In this regard, various criminal and non-criminal measures, both before and after crime incidence, are counted as prevention (Rajabipour, 2008: 70). "Prevention in its narrow and limited perception consists of measures and actions that are non-criminal in nature and are often implemented before the occurrence of a criminal phenomenon in order to prevent it from becoming actual" (Haji Dehabadi, XXX).

From a scientific perspective, prevention represents a logical-empirical concept that is symmetrically derived from some reasons and experiences. In criminology, prevention takes place outside the scope of the penal system, and denotes any action that seeks to prevent crime incidence; in other words, any measures taken to minimize delinquency can be the subject of preventive criminology. In this sense, preventive responses to a criminal phenomenon are the measures characterized by an action and a non-coercive nature to sterilize the society, resolve criminal crises, or disrupt previous situations (Najafi Abrandabadi, 2009). The prevention of sexual victimization of children and adolescents accordingly refers to the measures and actions taken before such individuals are abused.

Sexual Victimization Prevention Classification

In the related literature, criminal policy in relation to the prevention of sexual victimization is classified into three groups: action-oriented, situational, and reactive (Bagheri, 2018):

- a) Preventive (action-oriented) criminal policy against sexual victimization: This type of prevention, also called non-criminal prevention, is a set of non-criminal measures and actions that seek to prevent a crime before its occurrence by intervening in the process of crime actualization and a pre-criminal situation. This type of prevention is also divided into two categories:

social and situational. The social prevention itself is grouped into two types: community- and growth-oriented. The community-oriented prevention accordingly is to affect the social context and the public environment by taking appropriate actions and measures to eliminate or reduce criminals. The growth-oriented prevention also aims to prevent the establishment and continuation of criminal behaviors in individuals by identifying risk factors and strengthening supportive ones as well as implementing early interventions (Taheri, 2009: 396). In fact, the community-oriented prevention strives for eliminating criminal settings.

- b) Situational preventive measures against sexual victimization: This type of prevention includes non-criminal measures and actions that are to eliminate or minimize the opportunities for a crime and make the pre-criminal situation inappropriate by increasing the risks of identification and the possibility of arrest. The offender is thus prevented to commit a crime. This type of prevention seeks to disrupt the process of transition from a criminal thought to act, using non-criminal methods, viz. elevating the costs of committing a crime and diminishing the resulting profits. It also seeks to prevent crime permanently by making changes and reforms in the individuals and the society, and even making the citizens aware to comply with social rules through education, encouragement, and punishment. In fact, in the situational prevention, there is no look at the future, but disturbing the offender's plans at the moment of committing a crime. Actually, offenders see some obstacles that must be removed if they want to commit a crime.
- c) Counter-criminal (reactive) preventive policy against sexual victimization: This type of prevention, as a retrieval strategy, prevents people after the crime occurrence by some measures and actions in the criminal justice system to reduce the crime incidence rate by individual and collective intimidation and learning from the first crime and its reoccurrence. This type of prevention is based on the impact it has on the individual and society, which in turn is divided into two types: general and specific (Bagheri, 2018).

3. Methodology

This applied cross-sectional study with an exploratory objective was a descriptive survey, using a mixed methods (qualitative-quantitative) research design. In this study, the data collection method was fulfilled in three phases. In the first phase, library studies, including the study of domestic and foreign books and publications and searching the databases (the Internet) were exploited in order to design the model. Thus, the factors affecting sexual victimization were identified according to the theoretical and practical foundations of the research. In the next phase, the criteria retrieved were synthesized

using the Roberts' six-step research synthesis model, the duplicate components were removed, and finally the desired criteria were selected (Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Roberts' six-step research synthesis model

Identify the needs, do the primary searches, and elucidate the needs
Conduct research to retrieve the studies
Select, refine, and organize the studies
Provide the conceptual framework and match it with the data resulting from the analyses
Process, synthesize, and interpret the data to reach tangible outcomes
Present the results

Source: Authors development

The databases selected in this study included Science Direct, Google Scholar, Noormags, the Scientific Information Database (SID), Magiran, and the Comprehensive Portal of Human Sciences. As well, the keywords used for the search purposes were sexual victimization, sexual delinquency, children, adolescents, and effective factors. In total, 173 articles, dissertations, and books were evaluated with reference to the research criteria. Upon reviewing the sources, 36 Persian articles (published from 1993 to 2018) and 62 English cases (published from 1983 to 2020), were finally reviewed and synthesized (Table 1). In the third phase, a questionnaire was designed in accordance with the synthesized criteria and its integration with the expert opinions.

The questionnaire consisted of 90 closed-ended items to examine the effective factors in eight areas of social, economic, gender-related, family-related, demographic, media-related, psychological, and biological, whose validity was determined and confirmed by 15 experts involved in the fields of criminal law and criminology (n=8), sociology (n=4), and psychology (n=3), using the content validity index (CVR). In addition, the reliability of the questionnaire was estimated via Cronbach's alpha coefficient at 82%.

In the present study, a total number of 22 sex victims residing in the Juvenile Correctional Facility, Ardabil, Iran, and 43 sex offenders in prisons located in Ardabil, Iran, whose convictions had been finalized, were examined with the permission of the relevant authorities. The data collected from the sex victims and offenders were then

analyzed, using descriptive (i.e., percentage and frequency) and inferential (viz. Chi-square test and Fisher's exact test) statistics in the SPSS Statistics software (ver. 18).

4. Results

The study findings were presented in two parts. First, the Roberts' six-step research synthesis model was exploited to determine the factors affecting the sexual victimization of children and adolescents, as illustrated in Table 1.

The synthesis results of previous research after processing, synthesis, and interpretation accordingly revealed that sex offender's place of living, migration from rural to urban areas, drug addiction, parental divorce, as well as parental alcohol abuse and smoking were among the factors affecting the sexual victimization of children and adolescents, named as the social factors. In addition, sex offender's occupation, parental occupation, type of housing, family income, gift/money offers to sex victims, and educational facilities at school were labelled as the economic factors.

Moreover, preferring to dress as the opposite sex, tendency to communicate with the opposite sex, sexual desire, enjoying sex, watching pornography, seeing the intimacy and sex of others, witnessing the intimacy and sex of parents, and companionship with sexually victimized friends, were called the gender-related factors. As well, the causes of parental death, family conflicts and quarrels, being alone at home, having one's own room, and a sense of fear at home, were named the family-related factors.

In this line, sex victim's age, sex offender's age, as well as sex victim's gender, level of education, family size, age gap with friends, time of sexual victimization, age gap with sex offender, and sex offender's marital status were called the demographic factors. The use of satellite, having one's own personal mobile phone, use of mass media such as Telegram, WhatsApp, Instagram, etc. by sex victims were also processed, synthesized, and interpreted as the media-related factors.

Besides, sex victim's corporal punishment, swearing and insulting sex victims in the family, as well as their family breakdown, conflicts with siblings, strict parents, strict teachers, along with being mocked by family and receiving abusive behaviors by others, in addition to sex offender's depression, anger, high self-esteem, fear, isolation, lack of self-control, feeling of guilt or worthlessness or inferiority, and obsessive-compulsive disorder were named as the psychological factors.

Similarly, sex victim's weight, skin complexion, hair color, eye color, and physical condition as well as having many siblings and birth rank were called the biological factors.

Summarizing the results, the model for the prevention of sexual victimization of children and adolescents was presented, comprised of eight factors: social, economic, gender-related, family-related, demographic, media-related, psychological, and biological.

Table 1
The synthesis of the factors affecting the sexual victimization of children and adolescents in the selected studies

Processing, synthesis, and interpretation to reach tangible outcomes	Conceptual framework and matching it with the data resulting from the analyses	Selection, refinement, and organization of studies
Social factors	Place of living	Kazemipour (1998), Bakhshipour (1998), Kashefi Ismailzadeh (2000), Mahdikhani (2001), Smallbone et al. (2006), Bottoms et al. (2017), Savioja (2019)
	Migration from rural to urban areas	Kaur (2004), Péron & Grémillet (2013), De Schrijver et al. (2018), Delia Deckard (2020)
	Drug addiction	Negahi Mokhesabadi (2002), Madani Ghahfarokhi (2004), Naghavi & Fatehizadeh (2008), Nobles et al. (2012), Smallbone et al. (2013), Thomas (2015), Kirby (2015), Levenson et al. (2017), Letourneau et al. (2017)
	Parental divorce	Motamedi & Mostofifar (2009), Bagheri (2009), MacFarlane (1986), Price & Kunz (2003), DeKeseredy (2006)
	Parental alcohol abuse	Najafi Abrandabadi & Hashembeigi (2011), Mohseni (2013), La Fond (2005), Wortley & Smallbone (2006), Terry & Ackerman (2008), Bonnar-Kidd (2010), Nobles et al. (2012), Smallbone et al. (2013), Thomas (2015), Kirby (2015), Levenson et al. (2017), Letourneau et al. (2017), Stewart et al. (2019)
	Parental smoking	De Von Figueroa-Moseley et al. (2004), Kim et al. (2006), Arslan et al. (2016)
Economic factors	Parental occupation	Bakhshalian (1998), Mohammadkhani (2001), Madani Ghahfarokhi (2004), Smallbone et al. (2013), Levenson et al. (2017), Letourneau et al. (2017), Stewart et al. (2019)
	Sex offender's Occupation	Madani Ghahfarokhi (2004), Smallbone et al. (2013), Levenson et al. (2017), Letourneau et al. (2017), Stewart et al. (2019)
	Type of housing	Mahdikhani (2001), Bakhshipour (2009), Levenson et al. (2007), Smallbone et al. (2013), Kirby (2015)
	Family income	Bakhshipour (1998), Hatefi (1999), Kashefi Ismailzadeh (2000), Mohammadkhani (2001), Madani Ghahfarokhi (2004), Mohseni (2013), Hosseini & Safari (2015), Laws (1989), La Fond (2005), Bonnar-Kidd (2010), Smallbone et al. (2013), Kirby (2015), Levenson et al. (2017), Letourneau et al. (2017), Stewart et al. (2019)
	Gift/money offers to sex victims	Mohseni (2013), Levenson et al. (2017), Thompson (2020)
	Educational facilities at school	Atouf (2007), Davidson-Arad (2009)
	Preferring to dress as the opposite sex	Leila (2007), Clark (1996), Boesky (2002), McCuish & Lussier (2017)
	Tendency to communicate	Boesky (2002), Myers (2012), McCuish (2017)

Gender-related factors	with the opposite sex	
	Sexual desire	Leila (2007), Clark (1996), Zgourides (1997), Myers (2012), McCuish (2017)
	Enjoying sex	Boesky (2002), Myers (2012), McCuish (2017)
	Seeing pornography	Zgourides (1997), Boesky (2002), Myers (2012), McCuish (2017)
	Seeing the intimacy and sex of others	Boesky (2002), Myers (2012), McCuish (2017)
	Witnessing the intimacy and sex of parents	Leila (2007), Zgourides (1997), Boesky (2002), Myers (2012), McCuish (2017)
	Companionship with sexually victimized friends	Clark (1996), Zgourides (1997), Boesky (2002), Myers (2012), McCuish (2017)
Family-related factors	Parental death	Madani Ghahfarokhi (2004)
	Family conflicts and quarrels	Namdari (1998), Madani Ghahfarokhi (2004), Kazempour (1998), Velen (1996)
	Being alone at home	Madani Ghahfarokhi (2004), Bakhtiari & Hosseini (2004), Bagheri (2009)
	Having one's own room	Madani Ghahfarokhi (2004), Bakhtiari & Hosseini (2004)
	A sense of fear at home	Leila (2007), Bagheri (2009), Brett (2009), Shiravi (2010), Stuewig & McCloskey (2005), Smallbone et al. (2006), Curcio et al. (2013), Woodward et al. (2017), Savioja (2019)
Demographic factors	Sex victim's age	Asadollahi Haji Kord (2001), Maleki (2005), Pournaji (2008), Motamedi & Mostofifar (2009), Terry and Ackerman (2008), Nobles et al. (2012), Kirby (2015), Levenson et al. (2017), Letourneau et al. (2017), Stewart et al. (2019)
	Sex offender's age	Motamedi & Mostofifar (2009), Terry and Ackerman (2008), Levenson et al. (2017), Stewart et al. (2019)
	Sex victim's gender	Hosseini & Safari (2015)
	Level of education	Najafi Tavana (2005), Iman et al. (2011), Terry & Ackerman (2008), Finkelhor (2009), Bonner-Kidd (2010), Nobles et al. (2012), Smallbone et al. (2013), Thomas (2015), Kirby (2015), Levenson et al. (2017), Letourneau et al. (2017), Stewart et al. (2019)
	Sex victim's family size	Bischof et al. (1995), Baker et al. (2003)
	Age gap with friends	Kashefi Ismailzadeh (2000), Asadollahi Haji Kord (2001), Raijian Asli (2002)
	Time of sexual victimization	Mohseni (2013), Terry & Ackerman (2008), Finkelhor (2009), Bonner-Kidd (2010), Levenson et al. (2017), Letourneau et al. (2017, 2018)
	Age gap between sex victim and sex offender	Levenson et al. (2017), Letourneau et al. (2017, 2018)
	Sex offender's marital status	Terry & Ackerman (2008), Finkelhor (2009), Bonner-Kidd (2010), Nobles et al. (2012), Thomas (2015), Kirby (2015), Letourneau et al. (2017)
Use of satellite	Sadeghi Fasaei & Rajab Larijani (2010), Towhidi & Fazli (2014), Bagheri (2015), Letourneau et al. (2018)	

Media-related factors	Having one's own personal mobile phone	Peters & Bullman (1996), Choi et al. (2017)
	Use of mass media such as Telegram, WhatsApp, Instagram, etc.	Horowitz (2007), Kadiri & Muhammed (2010), Wijkman (2014), Wykes (2017)
Psychological factors	Sex victim's corporal punishment	Brett (2009), Green et al. (2002), Shannon (2009), Topçuoğlu et al. (2014), Stewart et al. (2019), Amran & Basri (2020)
	Swearing and insulting sex victims in the family	Bischof et al. (1995), Caputo et al.(1999), Siria et al. (2020)
	Family breakdown	Danesh (1991), Namdari (1998), Hatefi (1999), Mohammadkhani (2001), Catherine (2003), Madani Ghahfarokhi (2004), Bakhtiari & Hosseini (2004), Atouf (2007), Fakhraei (2008), Naghavi & Fatehizadeh (2008), Motamedi & Mostofifar (2009), Mullen (1996)
	Conflicts with siblings	Mullen (1996), Amran et al. (2020)
	Strict parents	Ryan et al. (2011), Stewart et al. (2019), Amran & Basri (2020)
	Strict teachers	Najafi Tavana (2005), Atouf (2007), Leila (2007), Abed Khorasani (2010)
	Being mocked by family	Curcio et al. (2013), Woodward et al. (2017), Savioja (2019)
	Receiving abusive behaviors by others	Rutter & Giller (1983), Goldstein (1991), Stuewig & McCloskey (2005), Woodward et al. (2017)
	Sex offender's depression	Rutter & Giller (1983), Goldstein (1991), Stuewig & McCloskey (2005), Smallbone et al. (2006), Curcio et al. (2013), Woodward et al. (2017), Savioja (2019)
	Sex offender's anger	Rutter & Giller (1983), Stuewig & McCloskey (2005), Smallbone et al. (2006), Curcio et al. (2013), Woodward et al. (2017), Savioja (2019)
	Sex offender's high self-esteem	Curcio et al. (2013), Woodward et al. (2017), Savioja (2019)
	Sex offender's fear	Rutter & Giller (1983), Goldstein (1991), Stuewig & McCloskey (2005), Smallbone et al. (2006), Curcio et al. (2013)
	Sex offender's isolation	Stuewig & McCloskey (2005), Curcio et al. (2013), Woodward et al. (2017), Savioja (2019)
	Sex offender's lack of self-control	Blaske et al. (1989), Haywood et al. (1996), Firestone et al. (1998), Fisher et al. (1999), McMunn et al. (2019)
	Sex offender's feeling of guilt or worthlessness or inferiority	Firestone et al. (1998), Fisher et al. (1999)
	Sex offender's obsessive-compulsive disorder	Goldstein (1991), Stuewig & McCloskey (2005), Smallbone et al. (2006), Savioja (2019)

Biological factors	Sex victim's weight	Wortley & Smallbone (2006), Levenson et al. (2017), Terry & Ackerman (2008), Letourneau et al. (2017)
	Sex victim's skin complexion	Wortley & Smallbone (2006), Levenson et al. (2017), Terry & Ackerman (2008), Smallbone et al. (2013), Letourneau et al. (2017)
	Sex victim's hair color	Terry & Ackerman (2008), Smallbone et al. (2013), Letourneau et al. (2017)
	Sex victim's eye color	Levenson et al. (2017), Terry & Ackerman (2008), Smallbone et al. (2013)
	Sex victim's birth rank	Wortley & Smallbone (2006), Levenson et al. (2017), Terry & Ackerman (2008), Smallbone et al. (2013), Letourneau et al. (2017)
	Physical condition	Terry & Ackerman (2008), Smallbone et al. (2013), Letourneau et al. (2017)

Source: Authors development

Upon identifying the factors affecting the sexual victimization of children and adolescents and synthesizing them with reference to the Roberts' six-step synthesis research model, a questionnaire was developed to examine the effect of each factor in practice.

The results of the study of 22 sex victims and 43 sex offenders in the city of Ardabil, Iran, showed that the significant factors contributing to the sexual victimization of children and adolescents were sex victim's level of education and time of victimization, as well as sex offender's age, marital status, level of education, paternal education, and maternal education ($p < 0.05$). In addition, only sex victim's skin complexion and hair color and sex offender's physical condition were significant with respect to the biological factors ($p < 0.05$). Considering the social factors, sex victim's and sex offender's place of living, companionship with sexually victimized friends, and presence in unsafe neighborhoods were significant ($p < 0.05$).

In addition, among the family- and gender-related factors, only the type of relationship between sex victim and sex offender and having friends who had been sexually victimized were significant ($p < 0.05$). In this respect, the only economically influential factors were sex victim's type of housing, gift/money offers to sex victims by sex offenders, sex victim's parental occupation, sex offender's occupation, income, family income, and educational facilities at school ($p < 0.05$). (As well, only sex offender's behavior and high self-esteem, and fear, and sex victim's fear were significant in terms of the psychological factors ($p < 0.05$). In this line, among the effective factors within the media-related ones, were the use of satellite and mass media by sex offenders, and using mass media and watching pornography by sex victims ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2

Demographic factors affecting the sexual victimization of children and adolescents

Factors	Sub-factors	Frequency	Percentage	Significance level
Sex victim's level of educational	Elementary school	15	83.3	0.000

	First-period high school	2	11.1	
	Second-period high school	1	5.6	
Time of victimization	Morning	3	13.6	0.003
	Noon	4	18.2	
	Evening	13	59.1	
	Night	2	9.1	
Sex offender's age	20-30	19	46.3	0.002
	30-40	13	31.7	
	40-50	6	14.6	
	50-60	3	7.3	
Sex offender's marital status	Single	21	60	0.000
	Married	11	31.4	
	Divorced	1	2.9	
	Separated	2	5.7	
Sex offender's paternal education	Illiterate	23	60.5	0.000
	Below a high school diploma	10	26.3	
	High school diploma	4	10.5	
	Associate's Degree	1	2.6	
Sex offender's maternal education	Illiterate	27	69.2	0.000
	Below a high school diploma	9	23.1	
	High school diploma	1	2.6	
	Associate's degree	1	2.6	
	Master's degree	1	2.6	
Sex offender's level of education	Illiterate	13	30.2	0.000
	Below a high school diploma	16	37.2	
	High school diploma	6	14	
	Associate's degree	2	4.7	
	Bachelor's degree	2	4.7	
	Master's degree	4	9.3	

Source: Authors development

Table 3
Biological factors affecting the sexual victimization of children and adolescents

Factors	Sub-factors	Frequency	Percentage	Significance level
Sex victim's skin complexion	Wheat	3	15	0.005
	Fair	12	60	
	Swarthy	2	10	
	Green	3	15	
Sex victim's hair color	Black	11	55	0.001
	Blonde	2	10	
	Dark brown	5	25	
	Golden	1	5	
	Brown	1	5	
Sex offender's physical condition	Healthy	37	94.9	0.000
	Disabled	2	5.1	

Source: Authors development

Table 4
Social factors affecting the sexual victimization of children and adolescents

Factors	Sub-factors	Frequency	Percentage	Significance level
Sex victim's place of living	Urban	20	95.2	0.000
	Rural	1	4.8	
Sex offender's place of living	Urban	34	82.9	0.000
	Rural	7	17.1	
Companionship with sexually victimized friends	Yes	14	67	0.000
	No	7	33	
Presence in unsafe neighborhoods	Yes	19	92	0.000
	No	2	8	

Source: Authors development

Table 5
Family factors affecting the sexual victimization of children and adolescents

Factors	Sub-factors	Frequency	Percentage	Significance level
Type of relationship between sex victim and sex offender	Brother	1	4.8	0.002
	Relative	11	52.4	
	Teacher	1	4.8	
	Other	8	38.1	

Source: Authors development

Table 6

Gender-related factors affecting the sexual victimization of children and adolescents

Factors	Sub-factors	Frequency	Percentage	Significance level
Companionship with sexually victimized friends	Yes	17	81	0.007
	No	4	19	

Source: Authors development

Table 7

Economic factors affecting the sexual victimization of children and adolescents

Factors	Sub-factors	Frequency	Percentage	Significance level
Sex victim's type of housing	Apartment	8	38.12	0.012
	House	12	57.1	
	Other	1	4.8	
Gift/money offers to sex victims	Yes	18	81.8	0.004
	No	4	18.2	
Sex victim's paternal occupation	Retired	1	4.8	0.000
	Employee	5	23.8	
	Self-employed	15	71.4	
Sex victim's maternal occupation	Homekeeper	15	79	0.000
	Retired	1	4.8	
Sex offender's paternal occupation	Self-employed	30	73.17	0.000
	Unemployed	3	7.31	
	Employee	5	12.29	
	Retired	3	7.32	
Sex offender's maternal occupation	Deceased	6	14.29	0.000
	Homekeeper	31	73.81	
	Self-employed	4	9.52	
	Employee	1	2.38	
Sex offender's occupation	Unemployed	9	23.1	0.000
	Self-employed	25	64.1	
	Employee	5	12.8	
Sex offender's family income	Less than one million tomans	21	53.8	0.000
	Between one and two million tomans	10	25.6	
	Two to three million tomans	4	10.3	

	Three to four million tomans	1	2.6	
	More than five million tomans	3	7.7	
Sex offender's income	Less than one million tomans	19	57.6	0.000
	Between one and two million tomans	9	27.3	
	Two to three million tomans	1	3	
	More than five million tomans	4	12.1	
Sex offender's educational facilities at school	Very low	14	32.6	0.000
	Low	6	14	
	Moderate	21	48.8	
	High	1	2.3	
	Very high	1	2.3	

Source: Authors development

Table 8

Psychological factors affecting the sexual victimization of children and adolescents

Factors	Sub-factors	Frequency	Percentage	Significance level
Sex offender's behavior	Kind	18	81.8	0.000
	Funny	1	4.5	
	Polite	1	4.5	
	Violent	1	4.5	
	Good	1	4.5	
Reasons for delay in informing others or parents after sexual victimization	Fear	14	73.8	0.001
	Maintaining face	3	15.8	
	Feeling guilty	2	10.5	
Sex offender's high self-esteem	Yes	28	70	0.017
	No	12	30	

Source: Authors development

Table 9

Media-related factors affecting the sexual victimization of children and adolescents

Factors	Sub-factors	Frequency	Percentage	Significance level
Use of satellite	Yes	33	80.5	0.000
	No	8	19.5	
Use of mass media by sex offenders	Yes	39	95	0.000
	No	2	5	
	Yes	15	75	0.000

Use of mass media by sex victims	No	5	25	
Watching pornography by sex victims	Yes	18	90	0.000
	No	2	10	

Source: Authors development

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The results of the research synthesis demonstrated that eight factors were effective in the prevention of sexual victimization of children and adolescents. The first factors were named as the demographic ones and then categorized. In this respect, the results of the study of 22 sex victims and 43 sex offenders in the city of Ardabil, Iran, showed that the demographic factors were sex victim's level of education and time of victimization, as well as sex offender's age, marital status, level of education, paternal education, and maternal education, which could contribute to the sexual victimization of children and adolescents, in line with the reports in the related literature by Asadollahi Haji Kord (2001), Maleki (2005), Najafi Tavana (2005), Pournaji (2008), Motamedi and Mostofifar (2009), Iman et al. (2011), Mohseni (2013), Terry and Ackerman (2008), Finkelhor (2009), Bonner-Kidd (2010), Nobles et al. (2012), Smallbone et al. (2013), Thomas (2015), Kirby (2015), Letourneau et al. (2017), Levenson et al. (2017), and Stewart et al. (2019).

The second factors were also called the biological ones. The synthesis results accordingly revealed that sex victim's skin complexion and hair color and sex offender's physical condition were effective in the sexual victimization of children and adolescents, which was in agreement with the findings by Wortley and Smallbone (2006), Levenson et al. (2007), Terry and Ackerman (2008), Smallbone et al. (2013), and Letourneau et al. (2018).

The social factors as the third factors were sex victim's place of living, sex offender's place of living, companionship with sexually victimized friends, and presence in unsafe neighborhoods. The literature also supported these results so that Kazemipour (1998), Bakhshipour (1998), Kashefi Ismailzadeh (2000), Mahdikhani (2001), Smallbone et al. (2006), Bottoms et al. (2017), Savioja (2019) had also considered the effect of the mentioned factors on the sexual victimization of children and adolescents.

The fourth factors were the family-related ones, particularly type of relationship between sex victim and sex offender, which could contribute to the sexual victimization of children and adolescents, in consonance with the reports by Namdari (1998), Madani Ghahfarokhi (2004), Kazemipour (1998), Velen (1996), Madani Ghahfarokhi (2004), Bakhtiari and Hosseini (2004), and Bagheri (2009).

The fifth factors were also categorized as the gender-related factors, among them, companionship with sexually victimized friends could affect the sexual victimization of children and adolescents. The research literature, i.e., Clark (1996), Zorides (1997), Boesky (2002), Myers (2012), and McCuish (2017) had also verified the obtained results.

The economic factors were the sixth ones, including sex offender's type of housing, gift/ money offers to sex victims, occupation, parental occupation, one's own income, family income, and educational facilities at school, which could lead to the sexual victimization of children and adolescents, in accordance with the results of the studies by Bakhshalian (1998), Hatefi (1999), Kashefi Ismailzadeh (2000), Mahdikhani (2001), Mohammadkhani (2001), Madani Ghahfarokhi (2004), Atouf (2007), Bakhshipour (2009), Mohseni (2013), Hosseini and Safari (2015), Laws (1989), La Fond (2005), Levenson et al. (2017), Davidson-Arad (2009), Bonner-Kidd (2010), Smallbone et al. (2013), Kirby (2015), Letourneau et al. (2017), Stewart et al. (2019), and Thompson (2020).

The seventh factors were categorized as the psychological factors, such as sex offender's behavior and high self-esteem and sex victim's fear, which could contribute to the sexual victimization of children and adolescents. The related literature, viz. Rutter and Giller (1983), Goldstein (1991), Stuewig & McCloskey (2005), Smallbone et al. (2006), Curcio et al. (2013). Woodward et al. (2017), and Savioja (2019) had also bolstered these results.

The eighth factors were named the media-related ones, including use of satellite and mass media by sex offenders, as well as use of mass media and watching pornography by sex victims, which were effective in the sexual victimization of children and adolescents, consistent with the results of the studies by Sadeghi Fasaee et al. (2010), Towhidi and Fazli (2014), Bagheri (2015), Peters and Bullman (1996), Horowitz (2007), Kadiri and Muhammed (2010), Wijkman (2014), Choi et al. (2017), Wykes (2017), and Letourneau et al. (2018).

According to the results of the present study and the related literature, the model developed here was approved theoretically and practically.

Tabla 10
The model

The model for the prevention of sexual victimization of children and adolescents	Demographic	Sex victim's level of education and time of victimization, sex offender's age, marital status, education, paternal education, and maternal education
	Biological	Sex victim's skin complexion and hair color, and sex offender's physical condition
	Social	Sex victim's place of living, sex offender's place of living, companionship with sexually victimized friends, and presence in unsafe neighborhoods
	Family-related	Type of relationship between sex victim and sex offender
	Gender-related	Companionship with sexually victimized friends
	Economic	Sex victim's type of housing, gift/money offers to sex victims by sex offenders, sex victim's parental occupation, sex offender's occupation, income, family income, and educational facilities at school

	Psychological	Sex victim's behavior, reasons for delay in informing others or parents after sexual victimization, and sex offender's high self-esteem
	Media-related	Sex offender's use of satellite and mass media, sex victim's use of mass media, and watching pornography

Source: Authors development

Suggestions

It was suggested to implement and evaluate the proposed model to prevent the sexual victimization of children and adolescents in further studies.

Limitations

In this study, a questionnaire was administered to collect the data; as a result, some respondents might have refused to provide real answers. As the study samples were sex victims and offenders in the city of Ardabil, the results should be extended to other regions with more caution.

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Bibliographic references

- Asadollahi Haji Kord, M. (2001). Investigating parental abuse of children in elementary schools for girls. Master's Thesis, Islamic Azad University, Central Tehran Branch.
- Iman, M. T., Yousefi, E., Hosseinzadeh, M. (2011). Women, harassment, and reaction: A study of female students' experiences and reactions to street harassment. **Iranian Journal of Sociology**, 12 (3): 63-93.
- Bagheri, N. (2018). Iran's criminal policy regarding sexual harassment, confrontation, and prevention. *Law Assistance Quarterly*, 2 (6): 419-433.
- Bakhtiari, F., Hosseini, H. (2004). The West and the phenomenon of single-parent families. **Strategic Studies of Women**, 24 (1): 230-237.

- Bakhshalian, A. (1998). The method and cause of parental abuse on female middle school students in Tehran. Master's Thesis in Psychology, Allameh Tabatabaei University, Tehran.
- Bakhshipour, A. (1998). Primary prevention of child abuse. Master's Thesis, Tehran Institute of Psychiatry.
- Paknahad, A. (2013). Legal-criminological analysis of sexual harassment. **Journal of Criminal Law**, 4 (2): 7-33.
- Pournaji, B. (2008). **Silent Death: A Look at Child Abuse**. Hamshahri Publications.
- Torabi, T., Rezazadeh Moghadam, H. (2017). Investigating the basics of juvenile delinquency from a criminological perspective. Fifth International Conference on Research Approaches in the Humanities and Management.
- Towhidi, A. R., Fazli, D. (2014). Situational prevention of sexual crimes. **Quarterly Journal of Jurisprudence and Family Law** (Nedaye Sadegh), 19 (61): 71-96.
- Haji Dehabadi, M. A. (XXX). **Criminology**. Master's textbook, Islamic Law and Justice Center.
- Hosseini, S. H., Safari, S. (2015). The role of female gender in committing and preventing sexual crimes. **Quarterly Journal of Criminal Law Research**. 3 (11): 147-167.
- Danesh, T. (1991). **Juvenile delinquents**. Tehran, Rasa Cultural Services Institute.
- Dehkhoda, A. A. (1998). Dictionary, Volume 2. Tehran: University of Tehran.
- Raijian Asli, M. (2002). The position of delinquent and victimized children in Iranian criminal law. **Quarterly Journal of Legal Perspective**, Faculty of Judicial Sciences and Administrative Services. 25 (1): 3-30.
- Rajabipour, M. (2008). **Fundamentals of social prevention of juvenile delinquency**. Tehran, Montaha.
- Sotoudeh, H. Mirzaei, B., Pazand, A. (2015). **Criminal Psychology**. Tehran: Avaye Noor Publications, 10th edition.
- Shiravi, M. (2010). **Criminal liability of sexually abusive people in the light of criminology**. Master's Thesis. Islamic Azad University, Central Tehran Branch.
- Sadeghi Fasaee, S., Rajab Larijani, M. (2010). A sociological study of sexual harassment of women in the workplace. **Quarterly Journal of Women in Development and Politics** (Women Research), 8 (3): 111-134.
- Taheri, M. A. (2009). Human security and preventive criminal policy against drugs. Proceedings of the International Conference on Human Security in West Asia, p. 396.

- Abed Khorasani, M. R. (2010). **An Introduction to the Rights of the Child**. Mizan Publication.
- Atouf, A. H. (2007). Prevention of child abuse in Iran and the United States. Master's Thesis, Imam Sadegh (AS) University, Brothers' Branch.
- Fakhraei, S. (2008). Child harassment as a non-educational phenomenon. *Education Magazine*, 4 (4): 59-77.
- Catherine, W. (2003). A reflection on victimization and its types. Translation: Ali Saffari, **Journal of Legal Research**. 38 (1): 259-302.
- Kashefi Ismailzadeh, M. (2000). Studying the situation of street children in Mashhad. Master's Thesis, University of Tehran.
- Kazemipour, S. (1998). Assessing attitudes toward corporal punishment of children and adolescents and child abuse. Broadcasting Research Center.
- Leila, H. (2007). Child abuse prevention. Master's Thesis, University of Tehran.
- Mohseni, H. (2013). Prevention of sexual crimes in Iran and the United Kingdom. Master's Thesis, Shahid Beheshti University of Tehran, Department of Punishment and Criminology.
- Madani Ghahfarokhi, S. (2004). Investigating the trend of child abuse in Iran based on its etiology. **Social Welfare Quarterly**, 2 (7): 163-190.
- Motamedi, H., Mostofifar, F. (2009). Human trafficking challenges and prevention strategies: Commissioned by the Cultural and Social Research Group of the Strategic Research Institute: Tehran: Expediency Council, Strategic Research Center.
- Maleki, H. (2005). **Street children and adolescents**. Aknoon Publication.
- Mahdikhani, P. (2001). Prevalence of child abuse, the most common patterns of harassment in secondary high school students of in Tehran. Research project of the Ministry of Health, Treatment, and Medical Education.
- Mirkhalili, S. M. (2009). **Prevention of delinquency**: A look at the criminal policy of Islam. Tehran: Islamic Culture and Thought Research Institute Publishing Organization, First Edition.
- Namdari, P. (1998). Investigating the prevalence of abuse in Khorramabad middle school students and determining the effective factors in it. **Iranian Journal of Psychiatry and Clinical Psychology** (Thought and Behavior), 9 (1): 62-70.
- Najafi Abrandabadi, A. H., Hashembeigi, H. (2011). *Encyclopedia of Criminology*. Tehran, Ganj-e-Danesh Publications, second edition.
- Najafi Abrandabadi, A. H. (2009). **Fair crime prevention**. A Collection of Criminal Science Articles in honor of Dr. Ashouri, Samat Publications.

- Najafi Tavana, A. (2005). Deviations and delinquency of children and adolescents. First Edition, Rah-e Tarbiat Publications.
- Negahi Mokhlesabadi, M. (2002). Child abuse and its prevention in Iranian criminal policy and international documents. Master's Thesis, Islamic Azad University, Central Tehran Branch.
- Hatefi, J. (1999). Stress in child victims of sexual harassment. Paper presented at the 4th National Stress Congress, Iran University of Medical Sciences, Tehran.
- Amran, M. S., & Basri, N. A. (2020). Investigating the Relationship between Parenting Styles and Juvenile Delinquent Behaviour. **Universal Journal of Educational Research**, 8(11A), 25-32.
- Arslan, M. M., Demirkiran, D. S., Akcan, R., Zeren, C., & Kokacya, M. H. (2016). General characteristics of child sexual offenders in Hatay, Turkey. **The Eurasian journal of medicine**, 48(1), 6.
- Baker, A. J., Tabacoff, R., Tornusciolo, G., & Eisenstadt, M. (2003). Family secrecy: A comparative study of juvenile sex offenders and youth with conduct disorders. *Family process*, 42(1), 105-116.
- Bischof, G. P., Stith, S. M., & Whitney, M. L. (1995). Family environments of adolescent sex offenders and other juvenile delinquents. **Adolescence**, 30(117), 157-170.
- Blaske, D. M., Borduin, C. M., Henggeler, S. W., & Mann, B. J. (1989). Individual, family, and peer characteristics of adolescent sex offenders and assaultive offenders. **Developmental Psychology**, 25(5), 846.
- Boesky, L. M. (2002). Juvenile offenders with mental health disorders: Who are they and what do we do with them? (Vol. 4). Lanham, MD: American Correctional Association.
- Bonnar-Kidd, K. K. (2010). Sexual offender laws and prevention of sexual violence or recidivism. **American Journal of Public Health**, 100(3), 412-419.
- Bottoms, B. L., Golding, J. M., Stevenson, M. C., Wiley, T. R., & Yozwiak, J. A. (2017). A review of factors affecting jurors' decisions in child sexual abuse cases. *Handbook of eyewitness psychology*, 509-544.
- Caputo, A. A., Frick, P. J., & Brodsky, S. L. (1999). Family violence and juvenile sex offending: The potential mediating role of psychopathic traits and negative attitudes toward women. **Criminal justice and behavior**, 26(3), 338-356.
- Choi, K. S., Lee, S. S., & Lee, J. R. (2017). Mobile phone technology and online sexual harassment among juveniles in South Korea: Effects of self-control and social learning. **International Journal of Cyber Criminology**.
- Clark, M. W. (1996). Characteristics of juvenile sex offenders who admit versus those who deny their offenses. Pepperdine University.

- Curcio, A. L., Mak, A. S., & George, A. M. (2013). Do adolescent delinquency and problem drinking share psychosocial risk factors? A literature review. **Addictive Behaviors**, 38(4), 2003-2013.
- Davidson-Arad, B., Benbenishty, R., & Golan, M. (2009). Comparison of violence and abuse in juvenile correctional facilities and schools. **Journal of Interpersonal Violence**, 24(2), 259-279.
- De Schrijver, L., Vander Beken, T., Krahe, B., & Keygnaert, I. (2018). Prevalence of sexual violence in migrants, applicants for international protection, and refugees in Europe: a critical interpretive synthesis of the evidence. **International journal of environmental research and public health**, 15(9), 1979.
- De Von Figueroa-Moseley, C., Landrine, H., & Klonoff, E. A. (2004). Sexual abuse and smoking among college student women. **Addictive Behaviors**, 29(2), 245-251.
- DeKeseredy, W. S., Schwartz, M. D., Fagen, D., & Hall, M. (2006). Separation/divorce sexual assault: The contribution of male support. **Feminist Criminology**, 1(3), 228-250.
- Delia Deckard, N. (2020). Constructing Vulnerability: The Effect of State Migration Policy and Policing on the Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children. **Journal of Human Trafficking**, 1-27.
- Finkelhor, D. (2009). The prevention of childhood sexual abuse. **The future of children**, 19(2), 169-194.
- Firestone, P., Bradford, J. M., Greenberg, D. M., & Larose, M. R. (1998). Homicidal sex offenders: Psychological, phallometric, and diagnostic features. **Journal of the American Academy of Psychiatry and the Law Online**, 26(4), 537-552.
- Fisher, D., Beech, A., & Browne, K. (1999). Comparison of sex offenders to nonoffenders on selected psychological measures. **International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology**, 43(4), 473-491.
- Goldstein, A. P. (1991). **Delinquent gangs: A psychological perspective**. Champaign, IL: Research Press.
- Green, L., Butt, T., & King, N. (2002). Taking the chaste out of chastisement: An analysis of the sexual implications of the corporal punishment of children. **Childhood**, 9(2), 205-224.
- Haywood, T. W., Kravitz, H. M., Grossman, L. S., Wasyliv, O. E., & Hardy, D. W. (1996). Psychological aspects of sexual functioning among cleric and noncleric alleged sex offenders. **Child Abuse & Neglect**, 20(6), 527-536.
- Horowitz, E. (2007). **Growing media and legal attention to sex offenders: More safety or more injustice**. *JIJIS*, 7, 143.

- Kadiri, K. K. & Muhammed, A. Y. (2010). Mass Media as Correlated of Children Behavioural Problems in Kwara State of Nigeria. **Journal of Media and Communication Studies**, 3(5): 198-202.
- Kaur, R. (2004). Across-region marriages: Poverty, female migration and the sex ratio. *Economic and political weekly*, 2595-2603.
- Kim, H. S., & Kim, H. S. (2006). Discriminative factor analysis of juvenile delinquency in South Korea. **Journal of Korean Academy of Nursing**, 36(8), 1315-1323.
- Kirby, P. (2015). Ending sexual violence in conflict: the Preventing Sexual Violence Initiative and its critics. **International Affairs**, 91(3), 457-472.
- La Fond, J. Q. (2005). **Preventing sexual violence**: How society should cope with sex offenders. American Psychological Association.
- Laws, D. (1989). **Relapse prevention with sex offenders**. Guilford Press.
- Letourneau, E. J., Schaeffer, C. M., Bradshaw, C. P., & Feder, K. A. (2017). Preventing the onset of child sexual abuse by targeting young adolescents with universal prevention programming. **Child maltreatment**, 22(2), 100-111.
- Levenson, J. S., Willis, G. M., & Vicencio, C. P. (2017). Obstacles to help-seeking for sexual offenders: Implications for prevention of sexual abuse. **Journal of child sexual abuse**, 26(2), 99-120.
- MacFarlane, K., Waterman, J., Conerly, S., Damon, L., Durfee, M., & Long, S. (1986). **Sexual abuse of young children**. New York: Guilford Press.
- McCuish, E. C., & Lussier, P. (2017). Unfinished stories: From juvenile sex offenders to juvenile sex offending through a developmental life course perspective. **Aggression and violent behavior**, 37, 71-82.
- McMunn, P. E. (2019). Psychological Characteristics of Sex Offenders (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University).
- Myers, W. C., & Chan, H. C. (2012). Juvenile homosexual homicide. **Behavioral Sciences & the Law**, 30(2), 90-102.
- Nobles, M. R., Levenson, J. S., & Youstin, T. J. (2012). Effectiveness of residence restrictions in preventing sex offense recidivism. **Crime & Delinquency**, 58(4), 491-513.
- Péron, C., & Grémillet, D. (2013). Tracking through life stages: adult, immature and juvenile autumn migration in a long-lived seabird. **PloS one**, 8(8), e72713.
- Peters, M., & Bullman, S. (1996). Evaluation of the impact of boot camps for juvenile offenders: Mobile interim report. In Washington, DC: US Department of Justice.
- Price, C., & Kunz, J. (2003). Rethinking the paradigm of juvenile delinquency as related to divorce. **Journal of Divorce & Remarriage**, 39(1-2), 109-133.

- Rutter, M., & Giller, H. (1983). **Juvenile delinquency: Trends and perspectives**.
- Ryan, G., Leversee, T. F., & Lane, S. (2011). **Juvenile sexual offending: Causes, consequences, and correction**. John Wiley & Sons.
- Savioja, H. (2019). Sexual behavior in adolescence: The role of depression, delinquency, and family-related factors. (Tampere University Dissertations - Tampereen yliopiston väitöskirjat; No. 41). <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-03-1018-9>.
- Siria, S., Echeburúa, E., & Amor, P. (2020). Characteristics and risk factors in juvenile sexual offenders. **Psicothema** 2020, Vol. 32, No. 3, 314-321.
- Smallbone, S. W. (2006). Social and psychological factors in the development of delinquency and sexual deviance. **The juvenile sex offender**, 2, 211-225.
- Smallbone, S., Marshall, W. L., & Wortley, R. (2013). **Preventing child sexual abuse: Evidence, policy and practice**. Willan.
- Stewart, K. E., Sitney, M. H., Kaufman, K. L., DeStefano, J., & Bui, T. (2019). Preventing juvenile sexual offending through parental monitoring: a comparison study of youth's experiences of supervision. **Journal of Sexual Aggression**, 25(1), 16-30.
- Stuewig, J., & McCloskey, L. A. (2005). The relation of child maltreatment to shame and guilt among adolescents: Psychological routes to depression and delinquency. **Child maltreatment**, 10(4), 324-336.
- Terry, K. J., & Ackerman, A. (2008). Child sexual abuse in the Catholic Church: How situational crime prevention strategies can help create safe environments. **Criminal justice and behavior**, 35(5), 643-657.
- Thomas, T. (2015). **Sex crime: Sex offending and society**. Routledge.
- Thompson, M., Davis, L., Pendleton, V., & Schlafer, R. (2020). Differences in Sexual Health Outcomes between Adolescents in Public Schools and Juvenile Correctional Facilities. **Journal of Correctional Health Care**, 26(4), 327-337.
- Topçuoğlu, T., Eisner, M. P., & Ribeaud, D. (2014). Sex differences in the effects of parents' use of corporal punishment on children's aggressive behavior. In **Annales de la Faculté de Droit d'Istanbul** (Vol. 46, No. 63, pp. 185-218).
- Wijkman, M., Bijleveld, C., & Hendriks, J. (2014). Juvenile female sex offenders: Offender and offence characteristics. **European journal of criminology**, 11(1), 23-38.
- Woodward, V. H., Evans, M., & Brooks, M. (2017). Social and psychological factors of rural youth sexting: An examination of gender-specific models. **Deviant behavior**, 38(4), 461-476.
- Wortley, R., & Smallbone, S. (2006). Situational prevention of child sexual abuse (Vol. 19). Monsey, NY: Criminal Justice Press.

- Wykes, M. (2017). **Social media, cyberspace, and sex crime**. In The Oxford Handbook of Sex Offences and Sex Offenders.
- Zgourides, G., Monto, M., & Harris, R. (1997). Correlates of adolescent male sexual offense: Prior adult sexual contact, sexual attitudes, and use of sexually explicit materials. **International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology**, 41(3), 272-283.